

**IMPROVEMENT OF THE TASK AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF
MATHEMATICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCE LITERACY OF FUTURE
CHEMISTRY TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF IX ADAPTATION TO THE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS**

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Annotation; *The aim of the study is to form the literacy of future chemistry teachers based on the development and adaptation to the educational process of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers. Based on the tasks, the methods of using information communications, pedagogical technologies and the integration of sciences in the formation of natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher were explained.*

In the context of the widespread introduction of international assessment programs into the educational system of our country, future chemistry teachers studied methods and methodological conditions for the development of reading, mathematical and natural science literacy and creative activity. Based on the research, analysis of the results of international studies in the system of continuing education, the following were studied: creative activity, methodological structure and components of the formation of natural science literacy through interdisciplinary integration, by clarifying the scientific and methodological content of the preparation of the future chemistry teacher for international evaluation research.

The study was conducted among students of the 3rd year of higher education institution. According to the results obtained, a mathematical and statistical analysis was carried out, according to which the efficiency increased by 16%.

The purpose of the study, the development and adaptation of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers in the educational process, ways of forming the literacy of future chemistry teachers, the correct interpretation of the concept of integration.

Keywords: *CSR, ICT, OECD, PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS*

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Introduction. *In the PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS programs implemented by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD - Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development), today important factors are: widespread use of scientific achievements and innovative activities in the education system, sustainable*

development of all spheres of society and the state, reflection of comparative educational results.

It is a generally recognized fact that education in developed foreign countries is a social process that actively influences the domestic policy of the country. Due to this, the amount allocated for the economic support of school life in foreign countries increases from year to year. It is important to achieve a positive result by participating in international assessment programs in the field of education, qualitative changes and high efficiency, as well as compliance with international educational requirements, student reading, mathematical, natural science literacy and creative thinking, to form competencies for the successful use of the acquired knowledge. [3; 85-86-b].

The purpose of the study. Formation of the literacy of future chemistry teachers based on the development and adaptation to the educational process of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers.

In our country, on the basis of advanced foreign experience, reforms are being carried out aimed at ensuring the development of modern competence-based approaches in the system of general secondary education, which provides for the formation of educational and cognitive competencies for the system of continuing education among students. A number of works are being carried out to create an educational environment aimed at modernizing the content of modern education, creating the necessary conditions to realize their internal capabilities in the formation of educational and cognitive competencies among teachers [4; 471-477-b].

In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", PD-5712 rating of the international PISA program by 2030 defines the tasks to achieve entry into the top 30 advanced countries of the world and the creation of a national system.

The degree of knowledge of the problem. The state of preparation for the participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the International Evaluation Study and the development of tasks for the development of scientific literacy of students and the organization of seminars, was entrusted to a number of experts A.Radzhiev, A.A.Ismailov, H.Zh.To Daminov, N.A.Karimov, G.O.Togaeva, K.K.Karimberdiyev, Z.A.Kosimova, G.A.Pirimova, D. Askarova, S.R.Akbarova, M. Boymuratova. The curriculum and training seminars created by them reflect aspects of the formation of students' literacy in international student assessment studies [5; 9-22-b].

In order to improve the quality of education and prepare for international assessment systems in the CIS countries, several scientists are conducting experimental and research work. For example: G.S. Kovaleva, L.O. Roslova, G.A. Sidorova, A.Y. Pentin, N.A.Avdenko, evaluation of creative thinking in the context of international PISA research and development; from the point of view of the concept of creative activity of a teacher, as well as possible ways of its formation and development I.P.Nikitin, I.P.Goda, N.Ya.Khryasheva; the main content of the formation of creative abilities of the future chemistry teacher I.Suksiks, E.Zir, O. Butorina.

In the context of international research, it is possible to cite research works aimed at assessing and developing creative thinking, analyzing the results of international evaluation studies of students, studying, developing mathematical, natural science literacy of foreign scientists M. Hamilton, B.Maddox and K. Eddy, A.V. Wieseman, H.D. Meyer and A. Benavo, Barroso de Carvalho, E.Hanushek, V. Ludger, H. Rindermann and S.J. Cesi, Andreas Schleicher, Estado Sao Paulo.

Literature and scientific research consist of problems identified as a result of studying the work:

research work aimed at improving the mathematical literacy of future chemistry teachers has not been studied;

the fact that the future chemist did not conduct research work to improve the natural science literacy of the teacher;

integration of sciences is not used in the formation of natural science literacy of a future chemistry teacher;

it was found that the future chemistry teacher did not study the methods of scientific interpretation of natural phenomena in the formation of natural science literacy.

Goals and objectives of the study based on the identified problems:

tasks aimed at improving the mathematical literacy of future chemistry teachers create some;

development of didactic materials to improve the natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher;

development of a methodology for using the integration of sciences in the formation of natural science literacy of a future chemistry teacher;

development of methods of scientific interpretation of natural phenomena in the formation of natural science literacy in a future chemistry teacher;

the formation of the literacy of future chemistry teachers is based on the adaptation of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers to the educational process.

Materials and methods. In the context of the widespread introduction of international assessment programs into the education system of our country, the study by future chemistry teachers of methods and methodological conditions for the development of mathematical and natural science literacy and creative activity;

creative activity, methodological structure and components of the formation of natural science literacy by clarifying the scientific and methodological content of the preparation of a future chemistry teacher for an international evaluation study based on research, analysis of the results of international research in the system of continuing education, study through interdisciplinary integration;

integrative scientific and practical competence of a future chemistry teacher in the development of systematic assessment programs and natural science literacy in the functional development of motivation skills of educational and cognitive activity development of tools for the development of creative activity and natural science literacy based on the approach;

on the basis of international evaluation studies, the results of monitoring the effectiveness of the methodology for the development of natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher were scientifically and pedagogically determined by experimental and test work, the results were analyzed mathematically and statistically, and in this regard, proposals and recommendations were developed;

it consists in developing a methodology for using information and communication and pedagogical technologies in the formation of natural science literacy in a future chemistry teacher [6; 300-301-b].

Tasks aimed at improving the mathematical literacy of future chemistry teachers can be formed on the basis of simple mathematical problems laid down when creating some. For example: answer a given task based on creative thinking and mathematical literacy.

Task 1: Is it possible to get a zero answer by subtracting the number four from the number fifteen? What mathematical expressions can be used to perform this task, if possible. Express your answer in the following lines.

Answer: _____

The task can be performed as follows. The number fifteen is represented by prime numbers (in the Kremlin alphabet). If we subtract four numbers from a Roman number according to its mathematical operations, we get a zero value.

Solution: 15-IV = 0

Future chemistry teachers are taught the same simple but creative thinking and tasks aimed at the formation of mathematical literacy, the methodology of their training.

To improve the natural science literacy of a future chemistry teacher, it is necessary to create a database of tasks in the form of didactic materials, collections of practical classes and project work. This kit or tutorial should include the following tasks. For example:

Task 2: Take a close look at the picture below. Perform the nuclear reactions shown in the figure and determine the answer in which the reaction equation is expressed correctly.

Task 3: Circle "yes" or "no" in accordance with the points presented below.

The use of the integration of sciences in the formation of the natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher when covering topics, classes are formed by the speaker using concepts related to the subject of chemistry, physics, mathematics, biology, astronomy and geometry, on the basis of which the literacy of future chemistry teachers is being formed increases [7; 1578-1580-b].

During the formation of natural science literacy, the future chemistry teacher prepares tasks for the development of methods of scientific interpretation of natural phenomena, and on the basis of these tasks are used to improve the literacy of future chemistry teachers [10]. For example:

Task 4: Carefully read the above text and find the disease in plants, which is expressed in the figure below. Pinpoint the chemicals used against these diseases. Write your answer in the following lines.

Based on the adaptation of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers to the educational process, when forming the literacy of future chemistry teachers, it is necessary to prepare contextual tasks similar to those given below and compiled using international evaluation studies [8; 234-237-b]. The reason is that such tasks are compiled on the basis of topics included in the training load. For example.

Task 5. Explain the process of performing a chemical experiment and the reaction mechanism listed below, based on the electrolytic dissociation reaction. Express the reaction based on molecular, ionic and abbreviated ionic equations. Write your answer in the lines below.

Comment:

The future chemistry teacher will have the skills to perform tasks based on international assessment studies to form the competence of scientific interpretation of data and evidence, as well as to prepare contextual tasks related to them. It is in the course of fulfilling the tasks set in the project work that they should give a scientific analysis of the results and conclusions obtained [9; 1570-1577-b].

You can form their own natural science literacy by completing the above tasks and teaching them to analyze their results.

Results: The use of tasks based on the integration of information and communication and pedagogical technologies of International Evaluation Research, gave a very good result. Students of the selected 2 groups of the 3rd year, (there are 25 students in each group, 50 in total. The potential of students of both groups is equal to each other). The first group is an experimental group, the second group of students is a control group. In the experimental group, classes were organized by analyzing the above tasks according to concepts based on information and communication and pedagogical technologies. In the control group, classes were organized in traditional ways (lecture, brainstorming, ping-pong). To analyze the knowledge gained, both groups were given the same tasks, and they were analyzed according to the results.

Quantity	Students in the group	Excellent rating	Good rating	Satisfactory assessment	Unsatisfactory assessment	Quality indicator
An experienced group	25	17	7	1	0	96%
Control group	25	11	9	5	0	80%
Difference in results		6	-2	-4	0	16%

As a result, expressed in the table above, it was found that the natural science literacy of students in the experimental group is 16% higher than the natural science literacy of students in the control group.

Discussion. The aim of the research is to develop tasks aimed at developing mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers and the formation of literacy of future chemistry teachers based on adaptation to the educational process [11].

In the course of the research, based on the tasks, the methods of using information communications, pedagogical technologies and the integration of sciences in the formation of natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher were explained [12; 62-68-b].

The research task was completed. For example:

some tasks were created aimed at improving the mathematical literacy of future chemistry teachers;

didactic materials were developed to improve the natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher [13; 82-85-b];

future chemistry was introduced into the reading process by developing a methodology for using the integration of sciences in the formation of a teacher's natural science literacy;

methods of scientific interpretation of natural phenomena were developed in the formation of natural science literacy of the future chemistry teacher [14; 1109-1114-b];

based on the adaptation of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers, the literacy of future chemistry teachers is formed for the educational process [15; 91-93-b].

During the implementation of the research in several disciplines, such concepts as the correct interpretation of the integral, the performance of tasks, and the scientific interpretation of tasks were mastered [16; 147-149-b]. Thus, we have achieved the goal we set for ourselves and were able to fully fulfill the tasks set.

When doing the research, it was relatively difficult for the future chemistry teacher to form the skill of working with tasks.

Recommendations based on the results of the study:

the use of integration of sciences in the formation of natural science literacy in a future chemistry teacher;

the introduction of tasks aimed at the development of mathematical and natural science literacy of future chemistry teachers into the processes of lessons based on their adaptation to the educational process has been more developed [17; 17-22-b].

it was noted that it is necessary to teach the scientific interpretation of natural phenomena using concepts in chemistry.

List of used literature.

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2019 йил 29 апрелдаги ПФ-5712-сон “Ўзбекистон Республикаси халқ таълими тизимини 2030 йилгача ривожлантириш концепциясини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида” фармони.

2. Ergashovich, S. I. (2022, December). PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR INTERNATIONAL EXAMINATION STUDIES OF FUTURE CHEMISTRY TEACHERS FORMATION OF SKILLS. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 3, pp. 121-125).

3. Ergashovich, S. I. (2022). TASKS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL EVALUATION STUDIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS*, 2(18), 85-90.

4. Ergashovich, S. I. (2022). THE USE OF INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT RESEARCH COMPETENCIES IN THE FORMATION OF THE LITERACY OF FUTURE CHEMISTRY TEACHERS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(12), 471-477.

5. Ergashovich, S. I. (2021). USE OF INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION STUDENTS FOR INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS ON" ORGANIC CHEMISTRY". *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 2(01), 9-22.

6. Ergashovich, S. I. Preparation for the International Assessment System Using Modern Methods in Teaching Students in the General Secondary Education System. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 300-305.

7. Shernazarov, I., & Xodjabayeva, N. (2022). XALQARO BAHOLASH TADQIQOTLAR MATERIALLARIDAN FOYDALANISHDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARNING AHAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1578-1582.

8. ERGASHOVICH, S. I., & ORIFJONOVICH, T. N. Clear and Natural in Teaching Higher Education Institution Students on the Basis of the International Stem Education Program Characteristics of Integration of Sciences. *JournalNX*, 6(12), 234-237.

9. Bektosheva, S., & Shernazarov, I. (2022). O 'QUVCHILARDA FUNKSIONAL SAVODXONLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1570-1577.

10. Ergashovich, I. S. (2019). THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING ORGANIC CHEMISTRY IN NATURAL SCIENCES AT ACADEMIC HIGH SCHOOLS. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 7(11).

11. Berdikulov, R. S. (2020). Developmental factor of chemical thinking of future chemistry teachers. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 2020.

12. Berdikulov, R. S. (2017). DEDUCTION OF CHEMICAL THOUGHT. *European Research*, (5), 62-68.

13. Berdiqulov, R. S. (2022). KIMYO TA'LIMIGA MANTIQ QOIDALARINI INTEGRATSIYALASH TO 'G 'RISIDA. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, (1), 82-85.

14. Berdiqulov, R. (2022). DEDUCTIVE ANALYSIS TEACHING CHEMISTRY LOGICAL QUALITATIVE FOUNDATION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 1109-1114.

15. Исмаилов, С. А. (2023). ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ОПЫТОВ СОВРЕМЕННЫМИ МЕТОДАМИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ХИМИИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 20(4), 91-93.

16. Ismailov, S. A., qizi Avazova, K. E., & Dangalova, A. A. (2022). THEORETICAL BASIS OF USING INTERACTIVE MEDIA RESOURCES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(6), 147-149.

17. Amanov, R. A. (2023). Formation Of Concepts About the Periodic Law and the Structure of the Electronic Shells of Atoms of Elements. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 16, 17-22.